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CBMcarb-DB, a novel curated database at the interface of the structural and functional knowledge on CBMs and their carbohydrate ligands

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Carbohydrate Binding Modules (CBMs) are a structural and functional diverse class of carbohydrate-binding proteins, classified and annotated in the CAZY database into different families based on amino acid sequence similarity [1]. CBMs are typically found as ancillary non-catalytic protein domains of modular enzymes, enhancing catalytic efficiency, but can also function isolated or associated with other non-enzymatic proteins. The number of newly identified putative CBM sequences is growing fast due to the exponential increase of sequence information derived from genomics, metagenomics and transcriptomics data, particularly for microbial organisms. CBMs show diverse carbohydrate-binding specificities between families and even within the same family. Several characterized CBMs are associated with bacterial and fungal systems that recognize non-crystalline cellulose and chitin, insoluble storage polysaccharides, and different hemicellulosic substrates^[1,3]. Recently, attention has been drawn to CBMs from bacterial pathogens and commensal bacteria, which can recognize the complex glycosylation of mucins [2]. CBMs interact with carbohydrates through various non-covalent interactions, such as hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic interactions, CH- π interactions, van der Waals forces, and electrostatic interactions. The ligand binding site of CBMs is usually composed of aromatic residues that form a flat, groove, or pocket-shaped surface that matches the shape and size of the ligand. However, other molecular determinants are involved in making a CBM-carbohydrate complex, and the network of interactions confer specificity for a given carbohydrate. Hence, CBMs are an excellent model for studying protein-carbohydrate interactions. Here, we will describe the development and application of CBMcarb-DB, a novel database dedicated to displaying and analyzing the 3D structures of CBM-carbohydrate complexes^[4,5,6]. CBMcarb-DB provides curated structural data about CBM-carbohydrate binding interactions, carbohydrate conformation, and functional information on binding specificity. CBMcarb-DB contributes to establishing an integrated web-based platform that combines structural and functional knowledge of CBMs and their carbohydrate ligands, important for exploiting CBMs for various biotechnological applications, including generating engineered CBMs with diverse new functional properties^[3].

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